

Getting started on BlueSky

A guide for scientists

Last update: Dec 3rd 2024; based on a [Guide](#) originally created by Jonny Coates

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An introduction to BlueSky & how it works

Bluesky is a federated network, meaning that it is built on a decentralized framework. This removes control from a central authority and places it with the users. This also provides interoperability between platforms. Potentially, this means that users could create their own platforms (Mastodon calls these “instances”). It also means that there may be future interoperability with Mastodon.

The other benefit of a decentralized platform is that it enables users to choose from various feeds created by the developers or other users, meaning they aren't locked into an algorithm. However, this means that things work a little differently than you may be used to.

Tips

- Likes don't help to promote content, so **repost!**
 - However, custom feeds can sort content in a variety of ways, so check the feed description if you have a preferred feed
- **Use hashtags** - they help specific feeds to capture your content
- **Follow feeds** of interest & create your own to really tailor your experience
- **Utilise starter packs** to get started and to find new people to follow; they're a fantastic way to smooth the transition and always find new people with shared interests
- **Follow many people** as the ability to create your own feeds means that to make your “following” feed interesting, you should follow many more people than you may have done so elsewhere.
- **Create a bio and add a photo.** Before you use the platform, make sure people who visit your profile know who you are; otherwise, they might assume you are a bot and won't follow you back or interact with you.

If your paper is getting attention on BlueSky, it will be reflected in its Altmetric score. In December 2024, Altmetric added BlueSky “[as a new attention source for published research.](#)”

Finding people to follow

The best way to find people to follow is to import them from other platforms using tools like Skybridge or by utilising “starter packs.”

Find the people you were following

The easiest way to find accounts from Twitter/X is to use the Sky Follower Bridge Chrome plugin. There is a [video and text-based walkthrough](#) on how to find the accounts you followed on Twitter/X.

Find new people to follow - Starter packs

Starter packs are user-created lists of accounts to follow. These may be grouped by themes or interests. Once you’ve gotten started, you can create your own starter pack too! You can use these starter packs to follow everyone all at once or to browse through for individual accounts. These can also include up to 3 feeds within the starter pack.

Some useful starter packs include:

- [Preprint experts](#)
- [Open Science researchers and experts](#)
- [Research integrity](#)
- [Open Research library teams](#)
- [People interested in Open Science](#)
- [People interested in scientific communication](#)

There are also numerous field-specific starter packs and other lists that you can browse and search using [this tool](#).

To create your own starter pack, navigate to “Profile” and then “Starter Packs.” You will be presented with a screen to give the pack a name and description. You will now be able to search and add accounts.

If you are moving from platforms such as Twitter/X where you might have had a big following, and you feel discouraged about having a small following on BlueSky, we have some good news. A [blog post](#) on LSE discusses examples of social media users ([Andrew Dessler](#) and [Katharine Hayhoe](#)) who compared the same post on different platforms. Their conclusions? The engagement on BlueSky is much higher than on other platforms, so despite a smaller following, you can still have engaging conversations

Feeds - follow timelines based on topics of interest

With BlueSky, you can select feeds based on specific interests, communities, or content types, offering much greater control over the algorithm's influence on what you see. To find interesting feeds, the built-in BlueSky search works well, although there are also third-party apps available.

Different feeds can promote and highlight posts in different ways (effectively allowing you to choose your own “algorithm”). Some feeds are simply the latest posts/reposts sorted chronologically whilst others are more algorithmic and prioritise content on likes/reposts and engagement.

To subscribe to a feed:

1. Navigate to “Feeds” & scroll down to “Discover New Feeds”
2. Enter your search term
3. Click on the plus icon next to the feed to pin the feed

You can quickly switch between pinned feeds by scrolling along the top menu bar or on the individual feeds to the right side of the screen. To locate all of your feeds, click the large “#” button or “Feeds” button.

Some useful feeds to follow for science & science communication are:

- Preprints
- Metaresearch
- Scientific Publishing
- AcademicSky
- Science
- Open Research

There's a full list of (>200) science feeds maintained by [Mark Rubin](#) available [here](#).

You can also follow your favorite preprint server to get their updates.

Account	Topics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BioRxiv BioRxiv: Animal Behavior and Cognition BioRxiv: Biochemistry BioRxiv: Bioinformatics BioRxiv: Biophysics BioRxiv: Cancer Bio BioRxiv: Cell Biology BioRxiv: Developmental Biology BioRxiv: Ecology BioRxiv: Evolutionary Biology BioRxiv: Genetics BioRxiv: Genomics BioRxiv: Immunology BioRxiv: Microbiology BioRxiv: Molecular Biology BioRxiv: Neuroscience BioRxiv: Paleontology BioRxiv: Pathology BioRxiv: Pharmacology BioRxiv: Physiology BioRxiv: Plant Biology BioRxiv: Scientific Communication and Education BioRxiv: Systems Biology BioRxiv: Synthetic Biology BioRxiv: Zoology 	<p>Biology and subtopics</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arxiv: Physics.soc-ph 	<p>Physics</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arxiv stat 	<p>Statistics</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PsyArXivBot 	<p>Psychology</p>

Table credit: [BlueSky for Scientists](#) by [Steve Haroz](#) and [Mark Rubin](#)

You can also create your own feed for personal use or to share with others using tools such as [skyfeed](#). To create your own feed:

- Check that there are no similar feeds already (<https://bsky.app/feeds>)
- Use a third-party tool (such as [skyfeed.app](#)) and follow their guidance

If you want to inject some of the content from feeds you follow into your main feed you can do this in the settings:

- Settings > Content > Following Feed > Show samples of your feeds in your following feed

Lists can also be used to follow specific groups of people rather than topics, or they can be used to quickly block a wide range of people.

You can get even more control over your feed by setting up your preferred options by going to Settings-> Content and Media.

One of the interesting options is the Following Feed Preferences. There, you can decide if you want to see only the original posts on your feed or if you would also like to see the replies, reposts, and quote posts.

Settings

BlueSky has a range of settings and features which you can find under Settings section on your profile.

Those include Moderation and Content and Media tools where you can mute, moderate and set your preferences about the content you see.

One unique feature is the ability to detach your original posts from quote posts. This helps to limit yourself from being “piled-on” as easily.

Accessibility Settings

To ensure you will never forget to make your posts accessible, you can go to Settings and Accessibility. There, you can find Accessibility settings that you can activate on your account.

Interacting with other apps

BlueSky creates individual passwords to log in to other apps and services. This helps keep your account more secure. To generate an app password, navigate to your settings (1) and then scroll down to Privacy and Security (2). App Passwords

On the

next screen, select Add app password.

Useful tools & resources

<https://www.sky-follower-bridge.dev/get-started.html> - Find and quickly follow people who have Twitter/X accounts.

<https://blueskydirectory.com/starter-packs/all> - To find starter packs and other tools

<https://skyfeed.app/> - create personal views and create feeds

<https://goodfeeds.co/> - To find existing feeds

 [BlueSky for Scientists](#) - A guide created by [Mark Rubin](#) & [Steve Haroz](#)

 [BlueSky Science-Related Feeds](#) - full list of (>200) science feeds maintained by [Mark Rubin](#)

<https://github.com/fishttp/awesome-bluesky> - List of tools for BlueSky

Acknowledgments

This [Guide](#) was originally created by Jonny Coates, with subsequent minor changes by ASAPbio.